

INTRODUCTION

Studying the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution on modernization of Turkey's industrial sector is relevant due to increasing competition in the global market and to new digital technologies and automation.

Technological advances such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and cloud technologies represent new opportunities to optimize production, improve product quality, and increase efficiency.

Currently, numerous industries in Turkey face outdated processes and equipment; approaches to reduce resource consumption and carbon footprint are also underdeveloped.

Modernizing the industrial sector requires retraining the workforce and developing new skills needed to deal with latest technologies. Adopting Industry 4.0 approaches can create jobs, increase productivity and boost economic growth in Turkey, as well as contribute to developing small and medium-sized enterprises, an important component of the country's economy.

Literature review

Industry 4.0 is the fourth industrial revolution based on using modern technology to optimize production. It includes introduction of AI, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, and cloud technologies, enabling creation of smart factories where equipment, systems and processes are interconnected.

S. H. Mian writes that the focus of Industry 4.0 is on automation, decentralization, system integration, etc. The authors note that its implementation is still limited by the human factor: adaptive thinking, cognitive, and computational skills are needed, mainly in information technology, data analytics, etc. [1].

According to M. Piccarozzi, Industry 4.0 is a new topic for scientists-economists, but no systematic presentation of this concept in scientific literature on management is found [2].

M. Arucu examines the industrial and technological activities in the digital transformation in Turkey [3]. T. Vahap & T. Cigdem examine the impact of Industry 4.0 on industrial transformation in Turkey. E. Yazıcı and H. Düzkaaya believe that Industry 4.0 is essential to maintaining Turkey's global competitiveness and economic growth [4].

İ. Kabasakal writes that Industry 4.0 requires transformation of business towards digital technologies and increased competitiveness in the global market. Cooperation between

business and academic institutions is fundamental to achieving innovation. The Triple Helix model attracts much attention from the Turkish government [5].

Industry 4.0 is being actively implemented in enterprises in Turkey with successful examples – the Ford plant in Turkey uses advanced technologies to optimize production and improve the quality of cars. Turkish Aerospace Industries is actively implementing digital technologies to manage aviation and space projects.

F. Kosanoglu and H.T. Kus propose a sustainable supply chain management model for the construction industry in Turkey that considers all levels of construction. The proposed model is based on building life cycle assessment and utilizes three main dimensions of sustainability: environmental, social, and economic [6].

A. Uzbeck et al. study the adaptation of textile enterprises in Turkey to Industry 4.0. According to the authors, ERP technology is used by only half of the enterprises due to high investment costs [7].

G. Sariyer et al. write that advances in intelligent technologies help managers of small and medium-sized microenterprises control production quality using sophisticated data-based methods. The authors propose a model (multilayer perceptron) that is being tested in a kitchenware manufacturing company in Turkey [8].

However, certain industries (such as the automotive industry), despite significant modernization and training in manufacturing and innovation [9], have not achieved success [10].

G. Salihoğlu et al. describe the problems of waste recycling and disposal and the use of renewable energy in Turkey. The authors write that the country supports a circular economy, i.e., related to recycling and disposal of certain types of waste [11].

H. Eroğlu proposed a new solar energy demand index to distribute solar power plants properly. The author created a map of energy consumption and distribution of solar power plants in Turkey, “Map of regional need for solar power plants” [12].

Thus, studying existing technologies and their compatibility with new solutions is necessary to effectively integrate new technologies in Turkey. A socio-economic analysis of the impact this transition has on employment, productivity, and competitiveness is essential.

An objective assessment of the current state of infrastructure in Turkey to support transition to Industry 4.0, i.e., technology availability, internet quality, investment availability, and energy efficiency level, is needed.

The article aims to study the impact of Industry 4.0 on industrial modernization in Turkey.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were publications in scientific journals devoted to Industry 4.0: Sustainability, European Journal of Science and Technology, Journal of Education and Humanities: Theory and Practice, Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy, Acta Infologica, Annals of Operations Research, Environment, Development and Sustainability, and others.

Literature on modern technologies such as IoT, big data, artificial intelligence, and their application in industry was also used.

Methods: analyzing statistical data on the state of Turkey's industrial sector, the level of technology adoption, and its impact on productivity. SWOT analysis: assessing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to implementing Industry 4.0 in Turkey.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Analyzing the sectors of Industry 4.0 of interest to the Republic of Turkey, the following components of its national economy should be highlighted:

1) **Energy** plays a crucial role in stability and providing the necessary high production capacity.

a. Priority is given to the transit, export and processing facilities of natural gas and oil. In particular, attention is being drawn to the gas hub project proposed by the President of Russia, V.V. Putin, which will allow efficient redistribution of incoming energy resources through the following gas pipelines: via TransAnnex, Blue Stream and Turkish Stream [13], the Trans-Anatolian Natural Gas Pipeline (TANAP) and the South Caucasus Gas Pipeline (BTE).

b. Second, there is **green energy**.

1. In particular, the Republic of Turkey is among the top ten leading countries in the use of hydropower. As of the end of July 2020, there are 735 hydropower plants in Turkey, the most productive being Atatürk (2,400 MW); Karakaya (1,800 MW); Keban (1,330 MW); Altinkaya (1,200 MW); Ilisu (1,200 MW), erected and operated by Türkiye Elektrik İletim A.Ş. (TEİAŞ).

2. Wind and solar energy is being intensively developed as an efficient source of electricity that can ensure economical consumption and provide backup capacity. Leaders in the industry are the holdings: Anel Enerji; CW Enerji; Seiso Energy, as well as Turkish divisions of European companies Enercon; Vestas; Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy; Alke İnşaat.

c. The **nuclear industry** is still a frontline **industry** for Turkey, as due to logistical problems encountered and construction delays during the pandemic, the first fuel element loading into the Unit 1 reactor took place only in 2023 [14]. The Akkuyu NPP, which is under construction

[15], will be the first of three Turkish nuclear power plants. The Republic of Turkey opted for cooperation with Russia, while for the first time in the industry a build-own-operate (BOO) scheme was applied, under which the Russian Federation is responsible for construction, operation, decommissioning of the plant, and training of specialists from Turkish citizens [16]. Negotiations are underway for the Sinop NPP project in 2024 which will provide electricity to the most important enterprises on the Black Sea coast.

2) The **automotive industry in Turkey** is known for its large production of individual components as well as vehicle assembly. The annual production volume is about 1.5-1.7 million vehicles. In 2024, Turkey is listed among the world's 20 strongest automobile manufacturers. First of all, we are talking about Turkish enterprises producing European and American cars, the packages of which are owned by Turkish holdings, together with the parent companies: Ford Otosan, ToyotaSA, Mercedes-Benz Türk and Tofaş-Fiat-Chrysler. In turn, the company's own production of electric cars of the brand TOGG A.Ş. becomes innovative – the abbreviation stands for Türkiye'nin Otomobili Girişim Grubu (lit. Turkish Automobile Industry Initiative Group), which belongs to the holdings: Anadolu Grubu (%23), BMC (%23), Turkcell (%23), Zorlu Holding (%23), TOBB (Union of Chambers of Commerce and Commodity Exchanges of Turkey) (%8). The first examples of T10X SUVs and T10F sedans with a total output of up to 435 hp are available in all-wheel drive and rear-wheel drive versions for pre-order in the fall of 2024. [14].

3) The development of **digital economy**, as well as information technology and telecommunications, is being rolled out by the largest local cellular operator Turkcell, as well as the digital divisions of the bank holding companies: İŞBAŞ and Ziraatbank A.Ş.

4) **Innovative technologies**, including Internet technologies, Internet of Things, systems of smart protocols for home and office equipment, development of artificial intelligence, blockchain systems, are currently underdeveloped due to lack of demand for specialists and brain drain to Western countries. On the part of the Republic of Turkey, the development is mainly carried out by large concerns and holdings: Koç Holding, Sabancı Holding, Eksim and Borusan. Aselsan, mostly related to the defense industry, is a leader in the field of electronic communication and security systems, as well as radar and electro-optical systems. Nevertheless, Western companies such as Botanalytics, AT&T, Cisco, General Electric, IBM and Intel are proving to be more successful and in demand in the market [17].

5) **Aerospace industry**

a. Production and development of aircraft

Russia's SMO in Ukraine led to creation of hundreds of repair and assembly shops for the AFU and Ukrainian representatives of the military-industrial complex, which supported further re-industrialization of the Turkish aviation industry by attracting significant investments,

ensured consolidation of material resources and localization of production from the position of the current fragmentation of post-coastal logistic supplies and created its own scientific school, which absorbed elements of NATO technologies and Eurasian developments from the APR countries.

Western-oriented business structures are the customers for armaments and dual-use products, especially in the field of engine building and navigation systems, which are being actively implemented at the plants of Turkish Aerospace Inc. (TAI). Aviation clusters of repair and modernization of Western designs created the required critical skills and accumulated sufficient knowledge applied today for NATO, Ukraine, and some Russian holdings. The first of these projects was the promotion and production of the TAI Hurjet combat trainer aircraft. Its modification under combat parameters and testing in various modes will help Turkish developers launch it in series on two main specifications Hurjet-B and Hurjet-C, allowing its use for training and combat sorties in the mountains and over the plains. Series production is scheduled for the end of 2025. Approximately in the same time frame, the fifth-generation multirole fighter should arrive from the design bureau to the assembly shops (its working index is TAI TF-X). By the end of 2024, only the stage of ground testing of the built prototype, which is based on the American engine General Electric (F404-GE-102), is still available, but for serial production a Turkish analog of the appropriate capacity of the necessary quality will be offered. Serial production is possible with significant fragmentation and localization of parts and equipment in Turkey and will take place in the next 5-7 years. In the field of helicopters, Turkish engineers were able to create several multi-purpose (TAI T625 Gokbey with two turboshaft engines of Turkish design TS1400) and attack helicopters, which are also still working on American engines LHTEC (Rolls-Royce/Honeywell) CTS800-4AT, which should also be eventually replaced by Turkish analogs.

b. SpaceDragon's space programs and collaborations

After sending the first Turkish astronaut into space on September 19, 2023, the Turkish Agency, at the International Space Congress in Paris, concluded an agreement with Axiom space to send a collaborator to the Lunar Station, which will be a prologue to implementation of the roadmap on low-orbit missions, in the Lunar Project, in the development, assembly and launch of satellite systems as part of an extraterrestrial constellation for remote sensing of the Earth. Turkey's space program itself started in 1993 and includes already successful launches of 7 satellites between 2003 and 2015. At the same time, the Turkish authorities announced building their own spaceport, because technologically Turkish scientists work in close cooperation with ESA (European Space Agency) and practically mastered all the key competencies and overcome critical points for the development of their own school of astronautics. The construction site for the spaceport will be identified either on the border of Somalia and Kenya or will be part of the possible space infrastructure in Anatolia.

At the same time, R.T. Erdogan confirmed that Turkey will build its own spacecraft in cooperation with Elon Musk and that a private Turkish astronaut will fly on SpaceX's Crew Dragon spacecraft.

Roketsan specializes in production of missiles and defense systems and is also a contractor of the Turkish space program. It has successfully implemented projects to develop national satellite launch systems and is developing systems to monitor various territories via GPS with Western counterparts.

In early 2022, the parastatal Turkish Aerospace Industries (Türk Havacılık ve Uzay Sanayii) signed a contract with Pakistan's Space and Upper Atmosphere Research Commission (SUPARCO), including orbital correction satellites and technical cooperation for their joint production.

These steps are being taken by Turkish solar system researchers against the backdrop of growing competition from Iran (satellites) and the UAE, working in cooperation with Joe Bezos, a competitor of Elon Musk, who has already managed to launch his satellite to Mars and is developing a rover to take soil samples on its surface. Australia and New Zealand, which has its own spaceport and a high-tech company for space research, are particularly fast developing private and public space projects. Therefore, the vector of extraterrestrial missions for Turkish researchers will increasingly polarize in Industry 4.0 in the form of choosing the right technological cooperation and co-participation in satellite launch preparation programs and astronauts themselves with the leaders of the international space industry – the United States, China, and Russia.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The prospects for introducing the Industry 4.0 concept in modernizing Turkey's industrial sector are very promising. In particular, technologies such as IoT, big data and AI can significantly improve the efficiency of production. Automation and optimization lower operating costs, which is particularly important for the competitiveness of Turkish enterprises in the international arena. Industry 4.0 enables more flexible production systems that can quickly adapt to changes in demand and individual customer requirements. Adoption of new technologies opens up opportunities for developing innovative products and services, as well as creating new business models such as the service model. The use of technology to monitor and manage resources can contribute to more sustainable production, reducing environmental impact. The transition to Industry 4.0 requires new skills and knowledge, creating opportunities for training and upskilling of workers.

However, to successfully realize these prospects, Turkey needs to overcome a number of challenges such as lack of investment in technology, and the need for training and

infrastructure development. Considering these factors, the right strategy and support from the government can significantly accelerate modernization and implementation of Industry 4.0 in the country's industrial sector.

REFERENCES

1. Mian, S. H., Salah, B., Ameen, W., Moiduddin, K., & Alkhalefah, H. (2020). Adapting Universities for Sustainability Education in Industry 4.0: Channel of Challenges and Opportunities. *Sustainability*, 12(15): 6100.
2. Piccarozzi, M., Aquilani, B., & Gatti, C. 2018. Industry 4.0 in Management Studies: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 10(10): 3821.
3. Arucu, M. (2020). Scanning the Industry 4.0 Ecosystem in Turkey: Digitization and Innovation Studies. *European Journal of Science and Technology*, (20), 50–55.
4. Yazıcı, E., & Düzkaya, H. (2016). Endüstri Devriminde Dördüncü Dalga Ve Eğitim:Türkiye Dördüncü Dalga Endüstri Devrimine Hazır mı? Eğitim ve İnsani Bilimler Dergisi: Teori ve Uygulama. *Journal of Education and Humanities: Theory and Practice*, 7 (13), 49–88.
5. Kabasakal, İ., Keskin, F. D., Kaymaz, Y., Soyuer, H., Balım, A. R., & Eryılmaz, E. (2021). Quantitative Analysis of Stakeholder Perspective on the University-Industry-Government Collaboration in İzmir, Turkey. In: Durakbasa, N. M., Gençyılmaz, M. G. (eds) Digital Conversion on the Way to Industry 4.0. ISPR 2020. *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer, Cham.
6. Kosanoğlu, F., & Kus, H. T. (2021). Sustainable supply chain management in construction industry: a Turkish case. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 23, 2589–2613.
7. Özbek, A., Yıldız, A., & Alan, M. (2021). Türk Tekstil İşletmelerinin Endüstri 4.0'a Adaptasyonunun İncelenmesi An Investigation of the Adaptation of Turkish Textile Enterprises to Industry 4.0. *Acta Infologica*, 5, 255–265. DOI: 10.26650/acin.910774.
8. Sariyer, G., Mangla, S. K., Kazancoglu, Y., Ocal, T. C., & Luthra, S. (2021). Data analytics for quality management in Industry 4.0 from an MSME perspective. *Annals of Operations Research*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-021-04215-9>
9. Günay, G., Aldemir, G., & Çebi, F. (2021). Innovation Efficiency in Automotive Industry: The Case of Turkey. In: Durakbasa, N. M., Gençyılmaz, M. G. (eds) Digital Conversion on the Way to Industry 4.0. ISPR 2020. *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer, Cham.
10. Akçomak, İ. S., & Bürken, S. (2021). Middle-Technology Trap: The Case of Automotive Industry in Turkey. In: Ferreira, J. J. M., Teixeira, S. J., Rammal, H. G. (eds) Technological Innovation and International Competitiveness for Business Growth. Palgrave Studies in Democracy, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship for Growth. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
11. Salihoğlu, G., Turhan, Ş., İpeker, G. İ., & Salihoğlu, N. K. (2021). Circular Economy in

- Turkey. In: Ghosh, S. K., Ghosh, S. K. (eds) Circular Economy: Recent Trends in Global Perspective. Springer, Singapore
12. Eroğlu, H. (2022). Development of a novel solar energy need index for identifying priority investment regions: a case study and current status in Turkey. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24, 8840–8855.
 13. Turkish Stream Project // Official website of PJSC Gazprom. Available at: <https://www.gazprom.ru/projects/turk-stream/> (accessed 30 May 2022).
 14. IAEA Chief Highlights Sustainable Energy as First Nuclear Fuel Arrives in Türkiye // International Atomic Energy Agency. Available at: <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/iaea-chief-highlights-sustainable-energy-as-first-nuclear-fuel-arrives-in-turkiye> (accessed 30 May 2022).
 15. Bir otomobilden fazlası // TOGG. Available at: <https://www.togg.com.tr> (accessed 30 May 2022).
 16. Zenginobuz, E. Ü. (2022). Türkiye için bir rekabetçilik endeksi 2023 // E.Ü. Zenginobuz, Özkardeşin S., Çelebi A Türk Girişim ve İş Dünyası Konfederasyonu (TÜRKONFED) ile Ekonomi ve Dış Politikalar Araştırma Merkezi (EDAM), 19-45.
 17. Ünver, A. (2022). İleri teknolojiler, enformasyon manipülasyonu ve dezenformasyon // Siber Politikalar & Dijital Demokrasi Programı. Özyeğin Üniversitesi: EDAM, 37.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Aleksey S. Kharlanov (Russia, Moscow) – Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Cand. Sci. (Tech.), Professor of World Economy, Diplomatic Academy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia. E-mail: kharlanov2009@mail.ru

Ivan A. Molchanov (Russia, Moscow) – Post-graduate student. Diplomatic Academy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia. E-mail: turkologist@gmail.com

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2022/12/01/kharlanov/>

Received: Jun 3, 2022 | **Accepted:** Sep 15, 2022 | **Published:** Dec 1, 2022

Editor: Vinicius Martinez. PhD. Université Paris Cité, FRANCE

Copyright: © 2022 Kharlanov, A., & Molchanov, I. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.